

The Role and Impact of Social Media in Morocco's 2021 Elections

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Résumé

Les médias sociaux et l'impact qu'ils ont sur l'opinion publique ont été discutés par divers chercheurs. L'étude actuelle examine le rôle des médias sociaux dans la sensibilisation des jeunes Marocains à la participation politique. Le but de cette étude est de déterminer l'impact politique des médias sociaux sur les élections marocaines de 2021, lorsque le parti au pouvoir a utilisé les plateformes médiatiques pour encourager les gens à voter. Pour collecter des données auprès de 100 étudiants universitaires, on a choisi un questionnaire basé sur la théorie de la dépendance du système médiatique. Les résultats indiquent que les médias sociaux influencent la position politique, car la majorité des répondants ont convenu qu'ils ont décidé de voter pour un parti politique en fonction des informations perçues sur les médias sociaux.

Mots clés : Médias, Médias sociaux, Politique, Décision de vote, Élections marocaines de 2021, Participation politique

Abstract

Social media and the impact it has on public opinion have been discussed by various researchers. The current study investigates the role of Social Media in sensitizing Moroccan young people to participate in politics. The purpose of this study is to find out the political impact of social media on the 2021 Moroccan election when the ruling party has used media platforms to engage people to vote. To collect data from 100 university students, we choose a questionnaire based on Media System Dependency Theory. The findings indicate that social media affects the political stance as the majority of the respondents agreed that they decided to vote for a political party according to the information perceived from social media.

Keywords : Media, Social Media, Politics, Voting Decision, Morocco 2021 election, political participation

Introduction

The Internet is revolutionizing our society, economy, and technological systems. It has become an important tool in our life as it is evolving every day. It is drawing the people closer together. According to the DataReportal website (Simon, (2022), the number of global internet users has soared to 4.95 billion as of start of 2022, with internet penetration now standing at 62.5 percent of the world's total population, which provides young people with a range of opportunities and benefits, including access to different social media platforms. Social media has gained momentum over time and it has become an important platform for disseminating political discourse. It is giving access to social networking sites (SNSs) for political information and engagement (Bronstein & Aharony, 2015). Multiple studies have consistently shown that the utilization of social media has a significant impact on shaping consumer opinions (Gionis & Tsaparas, 2013). Furthermore, Wilson and Dunn (2011) have highlighted the strong correlation between social media and communication pertaining to protest activities. These platforms play a crucial role in documenting events, disseminating motivating information, sharing content, and influencing the perception of content reliability. Thus, social media plays a prominent role in political campaigns as politicians use social media to disseminate their political agendas far and wide, and try to convince people to vote for them.

The successful 2008 presidential campaign of Barack Obama serves as a compelling example that illustrates the advantages of employing social media in political campaigns. He has been called the first social-media president (Kori, (2016). As he succeeded in using services like Twitter, Facebook, Snapchat, and Instagram. In Ukraine, Volodymyr Zelensky used social media as a platform for his campaign instead of town halls and election tents. He has scored a landslide victory. During his candidacy for the presidency, Zelenskiy adopted a distinct approach by refraining from engaging in press conferences or sit-down interviews. Instead, he actively utilized his social media platforms to disseminate his messages and share videos (Maryana, 2020). In the Moroccan election, political parties used social networking sites in their electoral campaigns to attract and entice voters to vote for them. They adopted digital communication technologies for their electoral campaigns. For instance, The National Rally of Independent, it has emerged as the biggest political party. Many factors contributed to its success, but a major one was the way the liberal RNI leader, Aziz Akhouch and his team used social media and technology as a tool to effectively interact with youth. They introduced their political vision and the list of their candidates for the municipal, regional, and parliamentary elections through media.

This study intends to explore how social media is used among Moroccan students and its subsequent association with their political participation. For this purpose, Google Survey has been conducted to measure how social media is used by Ibn Zohr University students.

Thus, the study aims to answer the following questions: to what extent do Moroccan University students rely on social media? Does social media influence Moroccan young people's voting decision?

It is hypothesized that the level of dependency of voters on social media for perceiving political information and the effect it exerts on their voting decision is highly effective.

Therefore, we have divided this article into three main axes. The first axis is dedicated to exploring the conceptual and theoretical foundations that interconnect the key concepts, providing a solid theoretical framework for our study. The second axis refers to the methodology used and the study's context, outlining the research approach, data collection methods, and the setting in which the study took place. This section aims to ensure the transparency and comprehensibility of our research design. Lastly, the third axis is focused on the analysis and discussion of the results, where we delve into the findings obtained from the Google Survey conducted among Ibn Zohr University students. Here, we aim to explore the extent of social media usage among Moroccan students and its potential influence on their political participation, specifically their voting decisions.

1. Social Media and Politics

1.1. Definition of Social Media

Social media has become an important platform for most people. It provides them with wide opportunities. For instance, in terms of social interaction, there is always a social connection between individuals; it exceeds the circle of friends and family to the world wide web.

Social media can have various definitions. Lucky (2013) characterized social media as a powerful tool facilitating the connection between individuals, enabling them to generate, share, and exchange information and ideas within virtual communities and networks, whereas Anthony (2009) defined social media as an inevitable tool for the vast majority of organisations worldwide. They depend on social media to spread their messages, publicize their projects, and launch calls to get funding. It allows them to interact with people worldwide directly as it is easily accessible, direct, and interactive.

Based on the conceptual framework proposed by Kietzmann, Hermkens, McCarthy, and Silvestre (2011), the functionality and impact of social media can be comprehended through a honeycomb framework. This framework outlines seven fundamental building blocks of social media (SM): identity, conversations, sharing, presence, relationships, reputation, and groups. By employing this framework, we can dissect and explore distinct facets of the user experience in social media and their implications for companies.

Figure 1: The honeycomb of social media

Note: This honeycomb framework identifies seven functional building blocks of social media. From “Social media? Get serious! Understanding the functional building blocks of social media”, by Kietzmann, Hermkens, McCarthy, and Silvestre, 2011, *Business horizons*, 54(3), 241-251

Identity: As described by Kietzmann et al. (2011), the identity functional block in the honeycomb framework pertains to the level at which users disclose their identities within social media environments. Platforms like Facebook afford users the autonomy to determine the information they wish to share and with whom, encompassing aspects such as their name, age, gender, profession, and location. Moreover, the authors elucidate that users can consciously or unconsciously share their thoughts, feelings, likes, and dislikes, thus contributing to the portrayal of their identity on social media.

Conversations : The "conversations" block within the framework, as outlined by Kietzmann et al. (2011), encompasses the level of communication taking place on social media platforms between users. Numerous social media sites are primarily designed to facilitate and encourage

conversations among individuals and groups. Conversations may differ from one person to another for different reasons. They can tweet, blog, meet new people, find true love and share new ideas. They can also spread their messages to influence humanitarian causes or comment about a political debate. As such, people can interact directly with political leaders through SM.

Sharing : The "sharing" block refers to the act of transmitting and receiving content among users within the same social media platform. This content can encompass various forms such as photos, comments, and videos. Kietzmann et al. (2011) emphasize that the term "social" inherently implies the significance of exchanges and interactions between individuals in social media environments. For instance, during a political campaign, readers forward different links to articles about the activities that a political party will work on. Thus, people increasingly exchange their opinions.

Presence : The "presence" block within the framework emphasizes the ability of a user to determine the availability of other users. This extends to knowing the virtual and/or real-world location of others. In the virtual realm, users can control their presence through status lines indicating availability or hidden status (Kietzmann et al., 2011, p. 245). Additionally, Kietzmann et al. (2011) highlight another implication of "presence" that intersects with other functional blocks, such as "conversations" and "relationships." For instance, companies should acknowledge that social media presence is influenced by the level of intimacy and immediacy inherent in the relationship medium, with higher levels of social presence likely to enhance the influence of conversations (Kietzmann et al., 2011, p. 246).

Relationship : The term "relationships" signifies the connections established among individuals. It reflects the level of association and interrelation between users. As described by Kietzmann et al. (2011), "relate" implies that two or more users share some form of connection that motivates them to engage in conversations, share social objects, arrange meetups, or establish connections as friends or fans. Consequently, the nature of user connections on a social media platform often plays a crucial role in shaping the type and manner of information exchange.

Reputation : "Reputation" pertains to users' capacity to recognize and assess the status of both others and themselves within a social media platform. For instance, political leaders need to pay attention to the content they share and how they talk to people on social media. Because once the post is shared, users can "like" content and comment on it. And some can create a negative impact on the minds of other users. Consequently, it is crucial for politicians to promptly address each negative comment. Having an online presence enables politicians to gain

insights into the emotions and viewpoints of their audience regarding political parties, providing an opportunity to prevent the emergence of negative sentiments.

According to Kietzmann et al. (2011), the concept of reputation within social media platforms encompasses various interpretations. Generally, reputation revolves around the notion of trust. However, due to the limitations of information technologies in assessing qualitative criteria accurately, social media sites often rely on automated tools, such as "mechanical Turks," to aggregate user-generated information and determine trustworthiness (p. 247).

Group : The "Groups" functional block in social media pertains to the ability of users to establish communities and subcommunities. On platforms like Facebook, when users express their appreciation for the same content by "liking" it, they form a community. Additionally, as highlighted by Parsons (2013), users can create communities by organizing their friends into distinct groups. It is also important to note that social interaction is very important for politicians because it helps them understand more the needs of people. Moreover, interacting with young people specifically engages them in an interpersonal interaction with politicians, and they feel like they are part of the change within their society.

Each of these completes the other functionally. For instance, as it is mentioned above, we cannot differentiate between Presence, Conversation and Relationship on SM platforms. People can find out more about a certain political party through the presence of politicians and the way it communicates with citizens. Through the conversations they build and their comments, politicians help citizens create a strong relationship with them.

By interacting with a political party on SM, people can experience an interpersonal social interaction, which makes them feel they are a part of social change. This is how they get engaged indirectly in politics. According to Carney (2022), social media platforms have evolved into a space where political conversations take place and serve as a means for political parties and politicians to connect with and engage voters. Through social media, politicians can share and spread their political agenda to advocate for people.

According to Bui (2016), social media plays a significant role in the competition between political factions. It has become a platform for politicians to connect with their supporters and the general public, enabling them to disseminate messages, express their perspectives, share information, and participate in political discussions. Social networking sites facilitate interactive communication and immediate interaction between politicians and the community, fostering a more engaging and dynamic exchange of ideas.

1.2. Definitions of politics

The definition of “politics” varies from one scholar to another. It first began with the Greeks. The term “politics” is from the Greek word “Polis” which means “city or states”. In those days, each city was an independent state, e.g., Athens, Sparta, Corinth, etc. According to Dowse and Hughes (1972), politics fundamentally revolves around the concept of power. They argue that politics arises when there are disparities in power. This implies that any social relationship characterized by variations in power is inherently political.

Mouffe (1993) describes politics as encompassing the potential conflicts inherent in human relationships. It encompasses the collection of discourses, institutions, and practices that strive to establish order and organize human coexistence within a context that is perpetually marked by political tensions. (p. 8). Politics in its primary meanings means the politics of the interests of the different groups in society. If we review the names and objectives of political parties in the West, we will discover that each of them represents different interests and ideologies, but they are committed to the major interests of the state, and are subject to the electoral law and civil work.

Politics can be characterized as a framework wherein individuals in public settings collectively arrive at decisions that hold binding implications for organizing society and its resources (Fuchs, 2008). Wikipedia defines politics as a range of activities linked to decision-making within groups and other forms of power dynamics among individuals. We can also define it as how the power and the influence are distributed within a given society or system.

Politics is closely associated with the activities of politicians, who are often seen as powerseeking and now in the digital world, politicians can influence citizens through the media, and people learn about politics and government from the news they watch on television and read in newspapers. Politicians are aware of the importance of the media; thus, they choose specifically social media to control and manipulate citizens.

2. Importance of social media to politics

Given the significant transformations occurring globally, particularly in the political realm, it is evident that the media exert a substantial influence on the trajectory of events. Nowadays, social media are used by people worldwide. Social media are a powerful tool for influencing political and electoral decisions. Trottier and Fuchs (2015) emphasize that the core components of politics involve the preservation or reshaping of a distinct social order through the dissemination of discourse and symbolism on specific platforms. Media outlets serve as a prominent

manifestation of politics, providing citizens with the most accessible means to observe and participate in the political process.

The audience witness parliamentary procedures, political campaigns, party activities, and political party scandals only through mass media. Social media is the fastest way to get all the sorts of information they need. Furthermore, political parties can engage with citizens and interact with them. Social media exerts a strong influence on political opinion and electoral decisions. Tolbert and McNeal (2003) argue that the media plays a crucial role in enhancing voter participation by equipping citizens with the necessary information to make informed choices during elections and fostering their interest in the electoral process.

Consequently, politicians share more content on their social media accounts to publicize their agendas and to send their messages directly to the audience. Besides, they try to answer a myriad of questions from citizens. Sharing helps them build a strong relationship with citizens. As a result, they manipulate citizens indirectly to vote for a specific political party. People, in general, relate to the media to get the information they need. Moreover, people share content even though they don't decide. According to Reisach (2021), people share content in disruptive phases when they are not sure what to believe or decide. They cannot distinguish between facts and rumors.

Therefore, other people read the content and like it, and the more the content is liked, the more it spreads fast, and it becomes a source of information even if it is based on fake information or rumor. Sometimes even journalists rely on online information. If journalists do not check the source of information and make sure it is not fake, they will help spread fake news. Hong and Kim (2018) assert that people and journalists rely on online information aggregators, which creates a self-fulfilling prophecy with a popular piece of information becoming even more popular.

Considering social media's importance in influencing people to participate in various political activities, politicians rely on social media to advocate, propagate, and manipulate people to vote for them. The liberal National Rally of Independents leader, Aziz Akhouch is largely regarded to have won Morocco's Presidential Election in 2021 because of his clever use of social media to spread his message to citizens to vote for his party. He did well concerning the digital campaigns as it has emerged as the biggest political party. In the United States, it is widely believed that Barack Obama won the Presidential Election in 2008 with his intelligent use of Twitter to spread his messages among the voters (Bimber, 2014).

President Volodymyr Zelensky of Ukraine exemplifies how politicians have effectively harnessed the power of social media to sway public opinion and achieve electoral success.

Similarly, the 2013 general elections in Kenya showcased the significant influence of social media in shaping the political landscape (Bing, 2015).

3. Conceptual Framework

In today's world, every institution includes the media in its system, especially social media. Because SM plays an important role in the development of institutions to the point that it has become the most important tool in any political party. Social media has changed political communication as it can be observed in different areas of political life like election campaigns. Politicians use social media to spread their messages and to share their agenda activities. On the other hand, citizens rely on social media to get information about politicians and political parties because it is easily accessible.

The Media System Dependency theory serves as the conceptual framework for this study, as it offers a suitable framework for understanding the interplay between three key entities: Audience, Media, and Society. In this context, the Media refers to various social media platforms such as Instagram, Twitter, and Facebook. Developed in the 1970s, the theory of Media System Dependency was formulated as a response to weak-effect models of mass communication (Ball-Rokeach, 1974; Ball-Rokeach & DeFleur, 1976). It seeks to examine and elucidate the role of media in society by investigating the dependency relationships within and across different levels of analysis.

According to Ball-Rokeach and DeFleur (1976), the dependency perspective relates mass communication with societal systems. In other words, people become more reliant on the media to establish contact with societal institutions (Rubin, Alan, Sven, 1986, p.185) Thus, if one hopes to understand and explain people's feelings, behavior, how they think, and the changes in their cognitive aspect brought about by information they get from media, one must take into account the interrelationships amongst audience, media, and society. (Ball-Rokeach & DeFleur, 1976).

Figure 2: Illustrates Ball- Rokeach and DeFleur, (1976) Media System Dependency conceptual model.

Note: This Media system dependency theory (MSD), from “A dependency model of mass- media effects.” by Sandra Ball-Rokeach and Melvin Defleur, 1976, *Communication research*, 3(1), 3-21

Rubin et al. (1986, p.185) posit that the dynamics of media influence revolve around the interconnected relationships among the societal system, media system, and audience.

- The relationship between society and the media: Access and availability to media hold significant importance as factors that shape an individual's media experience. The extent of media dependence on social institutions varies, influenced by the characteristics of political, economic, and cultural systems in place. The nature of this dependency is subject to variation depending on the specific context in which it operates.

- The relationship between the media and the audience: According to Rubin et al. (1986), the key variable in the Media System Dependency theory is the extent to which people utilize a mass medium, which is influenced by their information needs. This relationship between media usage and information needs varies across different media systems. In modern societies, individuals rely on media-delivered information to meet their functional requirements.

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- The more prominent the information needs, the greater the dependency on the medium, resulting in a higher likelihood of media influencing their thoughts, emotions, and actions.
- The relationship between society and the audience: Societies play a significant role in shaping consumers' needs and motivations for media use, as well as providing norms, values, knowledge, and laws that guide their behavior. The social system, in this context, can serve as an alternative to the media by offering similar services and fulfilling similar functions for individuals within society.

Media system Dependency has been used by many researchers since it was first introduced in 1976 to explain the impact of media on individuals or communities. Therefore, MSD is a suitable conceptual framework for interpreting and explaining the impact of social media on politics, especially the voting decision in Morocco 2021 elections.

4. Methodology

This study is based on a quantitative method for establishing the truth and it focuses on objectivity in data collection. My methodological reasoning is inspired by positivism. This approach which consists of describing reality as it is, explains why it is therefore objective.

The purpose of selecting quantitative research is to generate knowledge and enhance comprehension of the social world. Social scientists and communication researchers employ quantitative research methods to observe and examine phenomena that impact individuals. Aliaga and Gunderson (2002) defined quantitative research methods as instruments for elucidating issues or phenomena by collecting numerical data and analyzing them using mathematical techniques, particularly statistics. Thus, the quantitative method is suitable for this study. Besides, it relies on Media System Dependency as a conceptual framework.

4.1. Data Collection

The analysis presented here draws on an online survey, utilizing Google Forms to collect primary data. Survey research, as defined by Sukamolson (2007), involves employing scientific sampling methods and a structured questionnaire to measure the characteristics of a specific population using statistical techniques. In the past, there were concerns about the representativeness of web-based surveys as they did not include non-users, potentially leading to overestimated effects and magnitudes of significance (Boulianne, 2009, 204). However, these concerns have diminished over time due to the widespread usage of the Internet worldwide, making it a highly significant and influential tool. The survey is based on snowball sampling, a method where a

participant who meets the defined qualifications shares an invitation with other individuals who are similar to them and also meet the criteria of the targeted population (Berg, 2006). The questionnaire link is distributed to Ibn Zohr University students through the Facebook and WhatsApp applications.

The university students are adults, and according to Lenhart et al. (2010), 93% of young adults aged between 18 and 29 go online at a rate equal to that of teens aged between 12 and 17, and 81% of adults aged between 30-49. Further, according to the site of the electoral regulations in Morocco, the number of registered voters in the electoral list is 17 509 127, (54% male vs 46%, female). Furthermore; 8% of voters are aged between 18 and 24 and 19% aged between 25 and 35. Additionally, as stated on the Datareportal website, 31.59 million people use the internet in Morocco. Therefore, university students are the appropriate target group. They were nonrandomly selected; we chose specifically students of Ibn Zohr University in Agadir, as a case study, each respondent spent an average of 3 minutes answering the questionnaire.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1. Results

This chapter presents the last phase of the study which includes the results and discussion of the study carried out in the form of an online survey sent to Ibn Zohr University, as well as the discussion of the results. This part is devoted to the presentation of the various results that emerged from the empirical research carried out using an online survey, which consists of two study themes. The first theme concerns the relationship between society and audience, whereas the second deals with the relationship between media and the audience.

5.1.1. Demography

The majority of the respondents are males (54 out of 101), whereas females are 47. Their age varies between 18 and 45, 49.5% identify themselves as Master's degree students with 8.9% MA students in their fourth year, 13.9 identify themselves as Bachelor students, and 9.9% are in their second year and 9.9 as Ph.D. students, 55 out of 101 respondents participated in 2021 election.

Figure 3: Shows the percentage of respondents that participate in 2021 elections model.

Note : This figure was created by the author based on data collected from the survey conducted among participants.

5.1.2. The relationship between society and the audience

The first question seeks to determine whether young people use social media to get political information and to understand the importance of political information to the respondents.

Figure 4 : Indicates the percentage of the respondents that rely on social media to get informed about political issues

Note : This figure was created by the author based on data collected from the survey conducted among participants.

Social media is an important source of political information for young people. The respondents rely on SM 99% percent indicating they use social media to get informed about political issues.

5.1.3. The relationship between the media and the audience

Concerning what social media platform they use to get the news, social media is the most used by respondents, 84.9% of the respondents use social media. 57.4% check websites to read news, 39.6% choose television, 24.8 prefer listening to the radio, and 11.9% read newspapers. This indicates the level of dependency of respondents on media.

Figure 5 : Social media platforms that respondents used

Note : This figure was created by the author based on data collected from the survey conducted among participants.

The respondents were asked if they have interacted with electronic activities within social networks related to election campaigns, 69 out of 101 admitted having interacted with electronic activities, while only 32 declined having not interacted.

Figure 6 : Electronic activities interaction in social media

Note : This figure was created by the author based on data collected from the survey conducted among participants.

Concerning the nature of this interaction, those who admitted with yes, 51.53% of them, sent a link of an article to a friend, and 55.7 % commented on social media, whereas 47.1 published a post on their accounts.

Figure 7 : Nature of the interaction

Note : This figure was created by the author based on data collected from the survey conducted among participants.

While asking the respondents about which of the social networks played a greater role in a successful electoral campaign, 89.9 % chose Facebook, 32.3 % believe that it is Instagram, 28.3 % pick up Youtube, while only 16.2% select Twitter. According to Meta’s advertisingresources, Facebook had 18.95 million users in Morocco in early 2022. Based on the DataReportal website, the users of Twitter, Youtube, and Instagram in Morocco in early 2022 are 2.85m, 21.40m, and 9.30m respectively. Figure 8 shows the list of media platforms the respondents think they played a great role in the success of the electoral campaigns.

Figure 8 : List of media Platform

Note : This figure was created by the author based on data collected from the survey conducted among participants.

From these results, we notice a high level of dependency on social media. The respondents rely on social media to get all the news they need, especially political information. Based on Media System Dependency, the relationship between the media and the audience is the most essential element of this theory because it predicts the influence of social media on the audience.

5.1.4. The effects

To determine if social media increases political awareness, the participants were asked if their use of social media increased their political awareness. 84 out of 101 respondents agreed. Besides, 95 out of 101 agreed that social networks contributed to the evolution of the political consciousness of young people. All these results confirmed the existence of a direct political impact of social media on youth voting decisions.

6. Discussion :

The results of the study provide valuable insights into the extent to which Moroccan young people rely on social media and how it influences their voting decisions. The demographic analysis revealed that the majority of the respondents were male, with varying ages and educational backgrounds. This diverse sample allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship between social media and political engagement among Moroccan youth.

The findings concerning the relationship between society and the audience highlight the significance of social media as an important source of political information for young people. Nearly all respondents indicated that they use social media platforms to stay informed about political issues. This high reliance on social media demonstrates its effectiveness in reaching and engaging with the target audience.

Furthermore, the study explored the relationship between the media and the audience. The results showed that social media platforms were the most commonly used by respondents to access news, followed by websites, television, radio, and newspapers. This indicates a strong dependency on social media as a primary source of information among the respondents. Additionally, a considerable number of participants reported interacting with election-related content on social media platforms, including sharing articles, commenting, and publishing posts.

When asked about the social networks that played a greater role in successful electoral campaigns, the majority of respondents identified Facebook as the most influential platform, followed by Instagram, YouTube, and Twitter. These findings align with the popularity and user base of these platforms in Morocco, as indicated by available data.

The results also revealed that the use of social media has a positive impact on political awareness among the respondents. The majority agreed that their use of social media increased their political awareness, and social networks were credited with contributing to the evolution of political consciousness among young people. This suggests that social media serves as a catalyst for political engagement and has a direct influence on youth voting decisions.

The study confirms the hypothesis that Moroccan young people heavily rely on social media for political information, and its impact on their voting decisions is highly significant. The rise of social media has transformed the political landscape in Morocco, leading to increased citizen participation and notable changes in political practices. These findings highlight the need for

political parties and candidates to effectively utilize social media platforms to engage with the youth population and shape their political preferences.

However, it is important to acknowledge that this study focused on a specific demographic group and may not be fully representative of the entire population. Future research could explore the influence of social media on voting decisions across different age groups and regions within Morocco to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of its impact on the political landscape.

Conclusion

Social media sites have become one of the important tools used by people to get information, especially during electoral campaigns. This is why politicians spread their messages and share their programs and agenda through social media. The influence of social media on young people has received considerable attention from academic researchers. However, this study examines the role of social media in sensitizing Moroccan young people to participate in politics and finding out the political impact of social media on the Moroccan 2021 elections. The findings of this research show that social media has an impact on young people. Furthermore, social media affects their voting decision. These findings give politicians, political parties, and researchers a better understanding of the impact of social media. The findings also shows that young Moroccan people prefer social media to get the news.

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